

BATSS

#1 NEWSLETTER - SUMMER 2024

Welcome to the BATSS community!

At BATSS, we are committed to transforming the European battery value chain with safer, more efficient, and sustainable battery systems for transport and mobile applications. As we advance in this mission, we are excited to share our latest updates and achievements.

In this issue, you will find detailed insights into our project **milestones**, highlights from our presence at key **events**, our active participation in the EU-INGENIOuS **cluster**, and much more.

Enjoy reading!

First things first, what is BATSS all about?

At its core, BATSS is focused on developing **tailored Battery Systems (BS)** using an innovative macrocell modular concept. Our goal is to demonstrate these systems in **three specific use cases** through a prototype that defines BS requirements for **improved safety**. By integrating advanced cell technology and following Safe-by-Design principles, we are set to deliver a BS that not only meets but exceeds industry standards.

[Learn more](#)

MILESTONES

Initial specifications and requirements for the use cases

BATSS has successfully defined the battery system's initial specifications, requirements, and challenges for the use cases.

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Completion of the electro-thermal preliminary model

BATSS completed an early-stage model that will be instrumental in building a full battery pack simulation.

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NEWS

BATSS joins forces with EU-INGENIOUS to amplify innovation and impact

We introduce the EU-INGENIOUS battery cluster, a collaborative initiative within the Horizon Europe framework.

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Research & Innovation Agenda for battery research in Europe

Published in February, the SRIA 2024 outlines six key pillars that influence funding opportunities for projects

like [BATSS](#) and [VERSAPRINT](#).

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BATSS gains media spotlight: showcasing our research and innovations

BATSS has garnered significant attention from various media outlets in the initial months of our project.

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EVENTS

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BATSS at the European Conference of the Prognostics and Health Management Society (PHME24)

BATSS was presented at the PHME24, with an oral presentation and a proceeding related to the project's activities.

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BATSS shines at the “Empowering Europe” webinar

We are excited to share the highlights from our participation in the webinar “Empowering Europe: 7 new EU-funded battery research initiatives”.

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Transport Research Arena (TRA)

The TRA served as a strategic gathering for BATSS, offering insights into mobility trends across Europe.

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Coordinator

cidetec
energy storage

Partners and associated partners

 CIE Automotive

 ifp Energies nouvelles

 AIT APTERIAN INSTITUTE TECHNOLOGY

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 VUB VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL

 LOMARTOV [Spatial Innovation Engineering]

 Miba Miba Battery Systems

 FPT POWERTRAIN TECHNOLOGIES

Welcome aboard to power the future safely, efficiently and sustainably.

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